

Echoes of Muharram: Memory, History and Narratives in Andhra Pradesh

E N Mounika Sai, Assistant professor, Department of History, SVGM Government Degree College, Kalyandurg, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Dr E Nagaraju, Assistant professor, Department of Telugu, SYTR Government Degree & PG College, Madakasira, Sri Satya Sai District, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Abstract :

The commemoration of Muharram in Andhra Pradesh blends memory, history and narratives into a cultural practice deeply rooted in the local Muslim community. This paper explores how Muharram rituals and traditions serve as a means of remembering historical events and reinforcing religious identity. Through processions, recitations, and communal gatherings, participants engage in ritualistic acts that symbolize mourning and solidarity. These practices not only transmit collective memory but also shape narratives that intertwine religious observance with local socio-cultural dynamics. By examining the significance of Muharram practices in Andhra Pradesh, this study sheds light on how memory and history are constructed and transmitted within a specific cultural context.

Keywords: Muharram, memory, history, narratives, Andhra Pradesh, rituals

Muharram means "forbidden" or "prohibited" in Arabic. It marks the beginning of the Islamic New Year, commencing with the sighting of the new moon. This sacred month, also known as the Hijri month or the sacred month of Allah, holds great significance for Muslims worldwide. Muharram commemorates the death of Prophet Mohammed's grandson, Hussein ibn Ali, who was brutally martyred during the Battle of Karbala on the tenth day of Muharram, known as the Day of Ashura. In some regions of Andhra Pradesh, Muharram is known as "Pirla Panduga" or "Rottela Panduga." This reflects a blend of Hindu-Muslim cultural practices, particularly around the observance of Sufi shrines called Ashurkhanas. The term "Hindu-Muharram" is used in these regions to denote the joint observance of Muharram by Hindus and Muslims, emphasizing communal harmony and shared cultural traditions. Many people fast on the day of Ashura, during Muharram to increase their worship and also believe that their sins of the past year will be forgiven.

Significance of Muharram: The Battle of Karbala, a pivotal event in Islamic history, took place on October 10, 680 CE (10th Muharram, 61 AH), near present-day Iraq. It was a clash between the forces of Yazid I, the Umayyad caliph, and Imam Hussein ibn Ali, the grandson of Prophet Muhammad and the third Shia Imam. The conflict stemmed from a dispute over leadership and legitimacy within the Muslim community. Imam Hussein, supported by a small group of loyal companions and family members, including women and children, confronted Yazid's much larger army at Karbala. Despite being vastly outnumbered and facing severe thirst and hunger due to a siege lasting several days, Imam Hussein and his followers refused to pledge allegiance to Yazid, whom they viewed as a tyrant and unfit to rule. The battle

culminated in a tragic massacre on the 10th of Muharram (Ashura). Imam Hussein and most of his companions were martyred, including his six-month-old son, Ali al-Asghar. The events of Karbala hold profound significance in Shia Islam, symbolizing resistance against injustice, standing up for principles of truth and righteousness, and sacrificing one's life for the greater good of the community. The martyrdom of Imam Hussein and his companions is commemorated annually during Muharram, with rituals of mourning and remembrance that emphasize lessons of bravery, steadfastness, and unwavering faith in the face of adversity. These rituals serve to inspire generations of Muslims with the ethical and moral teachings derived from the sacrifices made at Karbala.

In many places in the Andhra Pradesh region, during Muharram, pir - deities (pir devullu) are usually installed outside the mosque as well as under banyan trees. These deities are normally three or five. Which represents martyrs Hasan and Hussein, and in some areas along with them, the prophet and his daughter Fatima and Ali. Pir deities also called panjahs – are a foot-long bronze installations and are usually in the form of an *isi* and *gurani* (sword and shield) symbolizing the brothers and their valour. Bamboo leaves are attached to them and the entire thing is tied with a red cloth. These panjahs are made of metals, such as silver, bronze, or brass, and are tied to long bamboo sticks and wrapped tightly in long pieces of red and green cloth sometimes they are decorated with garlands, umbrellas, and peacock feathers like in other parts of Deccan. Most communities offer prayer to the pir, active participation is mainly by the weaving castes such as *padmashalis*, *madigollu*, etc. The practice is popular among artisans such as weavers, potters, goldsmiths, blacksmiths, and all Muslim participants, most of who in this region are traders, merchants, or artisans such as blacksmiths, cotton cleaners, and dye makers. During the medieval period, significant migrations occurred, including many merchants moving across the Deccan in India. even as they settled different parts of the Deccan, these merchants continued to observe their cultural practices during festivals.

In this ten-day ritual, celebrated by the community, they offer many food items to the deities. It is associated with songs, sung in praise of Hasan and Hussein and the mourning songs relate to the tale and war of Karbala, where they died. Most of the themes composed by local poets from Muslims, *virashaivas* and other castes during the nineteenth century related to the practices of festivals found in the medieval period. *Pir devullu* rituals like *gramadevatha* (the presiding deity of the village) and the mother-goddess. These ten days they celebrate in front of the deities, performing dances, mainly "*dhula*", a folk dance is performed as part of Muharram celebrations. It is known as *hejjekunita* (feet dance) or *alavikunita*. The dance usually consists of eight to ten male members moving in a circle around the bonfire or *Alavi*, which is used to walk on the last day with the hope of getting boons from the deities. And they sing' s songs in praise of deities and they arrange carnival also. Such carnivals are colorful with folk dances, drum beats, dramas, songs, and circuses. on the ninth day, Hasan and Hussein are taken around the village in remembrance of the *kalaratri*, on the night of the murder. As the panjahs are taken around, the devotees offer water at the procession as it enters their streets (some people mostly men carry the deities and are taken around in the village, during that time the devotees come and pour water to their feet). On the tenth day, in front of the mosque, where men carrying the panjahs cross the bonfire. Like those supposed to be inflicted by evil spirits are also made to cross the fire to get cured by the pir after this, the immersion. Mostly men are

involved in this last-day procession when they bid farewell to the deities, like the immersion of idols in Ganesh Chaturthi, and on this day, panjaha are taken to a nearby river, pond, or other water body and immersed. This procession ends with the cleansing of the panjaha, which are tied back to the tree tops.

Memory in oral traditions involves transmitting experiences and knowledge through myths, customs, and rituals, crucial for affirming group identities. According to Misztal, oral traditions persist in societies where literacy is confined to a small elite in politics and religion. Group memories endure orally, passed down through generations via rituals and narratives, making it challenging to trace the origins of festivals. However, during these celebrations, cultural memories of ancestral roots are vividly observed. Epic poems recount events like those of Karbala, describing the place's horrors and detailing Husain and his army. These poems are orally transmitted and contribute significantly to cultural memory. Historical documents such as census records and gazetteers from the late nineteenth century onwards provide evidence of similar Muharram practices in South India and the Deccan region. These records highlight the enduring cultural significance and continuity of Muharram observances in these areas.

The ritual serves primarily as a form of social and collective memory among the people. It influences the emotions of participants; during this ritual, mourning is observed and alcohol is abstained from. According to belief, if a child is born on the day of Muharram, the festival is not celebrated for three years due to its considered *muttu* or inauspicious nature. The continuity and solidarity of groups are crucial elements within collective memory, emphasizing the cultural significance and communal bonds maintained through such rituals.

In some regions of the Deccan, festivals are celebrated in commemoration halls known as *ashurkhanas* (Hall of Fame). *Rotiyaan Ki Eid* or *Rottela panduga* is an annual three day festival celebrated at *Bara shaheed Dargah* in *Nellore* region of *Andhrapradesh*. In *Dargah*, they have made elaborate arrangements for the exchange of rotis by the people from far and near as a thanksgiving ceremony after the fulfillment of their wishes. Both Hindu and Muslim communities participate in these festivals. The *pir* deities are owned by certain families within the Muslim community, and some Hindu weaver families contribute money to prominent Muslim households that own these panjahas, thus gaining a share in their ownership (*perukistaru*). The question arises: why do societies or communities remember these deities, who were once human? How did divinity come to be associated with human forms? The *pir* deities, or these deities, were humans revered for their divine acts or sacrifices that pleased the gods.

According to Hobsbawam Eric, the concept of "invented tradition" refers to practices, rituals, or customs that, although appearing ancient and widely accepted, are relatively recent in origin. These traditions are intentionally created or formalized to instill certain values, norms of behavior, and a sense of continuity with the past. For instance, annual carnivals and other commemorative rituals like Muharram are examples of invented traditions that are celebrated generation after generation, reinforcing collective identity and historical connection through repeated participation.

Paul Connerton's research highlights how rituals and commemorations strengthen group solidarity by reinforcing a sense of collective identity which we can view in the Muharram festival. Through participating in these ritual behaviors, members demonstrate their loyalty and affiliation, solidifying the cohesive bond of "we" within the group. This phenomenon is particularly evident in professional communities where ritualistic practices serve to commemorate shared values and historical events, thereby nurturing a strong sense of unity and belonging among its members.

Conclusion: The practices surrounding Muharram in Andhra Pradesh intricately weave together memory, history, and narratives within the local Muslim community. Through rituals like the installation of Pir deities, the recitation of mourning songs, and the performance of cultural dances such as Dhula, the community not only commemorates the historical events of Karbala but also reaffirms its collective identity and religious devotion. These traditions, passed down through generations, serve as a poignant reminder of sacrifice, resilience, and solidarity. They not only preserve cultural heritage but also foster a sense of unity among diverse groups of artisans, traders, and community members who come together to observe and participate in these deeply meaningful rituals. By exploring and understanding these practices, we gain insight into how cultural memory is perpetuated and how history is continuously retold and interpreted within the rich tapestry of Andhra Pradesh's cultural landscape.

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